

THE EFFECT OF WORKING CONDITIONS ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN SOME MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN MOGADISHU SOMALIA.

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ABSTRACT:

Purpose: This study examines the effects of working condition on employee productivity in manufacturing firms, including work hours, workload, and training, and whether there is an influence of working conditions on employee productivity in Mogadishu manufacturing companies. **Design/methodology/approach:** The researcher employed self-administered questionnaire. 172 respondents from the specified industrial enterprises in Mogadishu, Somalia were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Furthermore, the study only looked at three working conditions; nevertheless, other factors may have an impact on employee performance. **Findings:** The study's findings have successfully confirmed that the study's key objectives were met. Furthermore, at manufacturing enterprises in Mogadishu, Somalia, the three determinants of working conditions have a beneficial effect on employee productivity. **Practical Implications:** This study assumed to provide fresh insights for the working condition in manufacturing companies in Mogadishu Somalia. Moreover, the study emphasis the level of manufacturing employees and their needs in training and development. **Originality/value:** This study highlights the practical knowledge of employees working conditions and provides contribution to the literature sources. It fills the gaps between the literatures by providing the great clarity in workers working conditions in manufacturing sector.

Keywords: Working conditions, working hours, workload, Performance, Training

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the 18th century, the number of micros and small businesses and people working in the informal economy has increased, accounting for most new jobs and the working poor. Safety and health at work, maternity leave, work-family conflicts, homework, hours of work, income from salaries, work organization, sexual harassment, workplace violence, workload, worker welfare facilities, housing, nutrition, and the environment are just a few of the issues millions of women and men face in micro and small businesses and the informal economy face. This program allows you to browse the internet and combines MSE and Internet Explorer (Rinehart, 2004; Ali, 2013).

In Pakistan's education sector, Khan et al. (2011) evaluated the impact of the working environment and infrastructure on employee performance and established a clear correlation between reward and employee performance. (Tesfu, Effects of the Workplace on Employee Performance: A Case Study of Bole Lemi Industrial Park, June 2019). The findings of a study conducted by Al-Omari et al. (2017) at a Jordanian engineering firm on the impact of the physical environment on job performance found a favourable association between the physical environment and job performance. They also urged companies to take the lead and establish a positive working atmosphere to increase employee productivity (Tesfu 2019).

Although various research on working environment concepts has been carried out in other areas of the world, there is a shortage of literature on Somalia. Since the 18th century, the number of micros and small businesses and people working in the informal economy has increased, accounting for most new jobs and the working poor. In Mogadishu, Somalia, there have been few studies on the relationship between the working environment and employee performance; hence, this study investigates how the workplace affects employee performance in Mogadishu, Somalia. Manufacturing enterprises in Somalia have experienced numerous changes, including failure and distraction, all of which have harmed the lives of employees and customers. The researcher highlights a concern that, with the formation of several manufacturing enterprises in Mogadishu, employees have been subjected to significant changes in their working conditions, including high staff turnover, staff shortages, and increased workload.

On the other hand, the employer gained a greater understanding of how the workplace environment affects employee motivation and performance due to this study. Employee performance is crucial to an organization's ability to meet its objectives. In the literature, employee performance has been demonstrated to influence working circumstances. Organizations should be aware of working conditions' impact on employee performance to take advantage of it and acquire a competitive edge. When it comes to workplace productivity, employee morale is typically connected.

As a result, the focus of this study was on the impact of the working environment on employee motivation and productivity in Mogadishu's industrial enterprises, as well as how operating hours affect employee productivity. This study's primary goals are to assess how working circumstances affect workers' productivity in Mogadishu's manufacturing businesses and to improve those businesses' expertise and performance.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Definitions of the Working Conditions

The workplace environment comprises the employee's work location and everyday activities. Depending on the nature of the working environment, the workplace environment has a good or negative impact on employee satisfaction levels. Employees might perform better in a comfortable setting. The office atmosphere has a direct effect on an employee's performance. Employee satisfaction is critical to an organization's success. Employees will perform better if the physical working environment is friendly. Several factors, such as the physical environment, influence employee satisfaction in the workplace. According to research, employees who are satisfied with their work environment have a lower turnover rate. Turnover is reduced when an employee receives a higher level of satisfaction. Dole and Schroeder (2001) state that Carlopio (1996) discovered positive job satisfaction.

2.2 Factors of Working Conditions that Affect Employee Performance

"Working circumstances" are "the workplace and all contemporary factors influencing labour, such as work hours, physical requirements, legal rights and obligations, corporate culture, workload, and training. Therefore, we use the working-conditions definition below. The phrase

"working conditions" refers to the workplace and the terms of an employee's contract (Manu, 2015). According to Armstrong and Baron (op. cit.), various factors influence performance, including the following: A person's ability, confidence, motivation, and devotion are all personal factors. (a) Leadership factors: the level of encouragement, counsel, and support Managers and team leaders offer this information. (c) Coworker assistance – the amount of help given by coworkers. Internal and external environmental pressures and changes in the System affect the organization's work environment and facilities (labour instruments) that need to be considered (Charles et al., 2014; Ali, 2013).

2.3 Workload

This refers to the amount of time spent on specific tasks. As a result, employees experience mental stress. Stress is a mental state that occurs when faced with both a challenge and an opportunity (Khan et al., 2019). On the other hand, Allen (1996) defined the term workload as a faculty member's total time spent on teaching, research, administration, and community service (S Khan, Azhar, Parveen, Naeem, and Sohail, July 2019).

2.4 Training

According to Nassazi (2013), employee training is critical for enhancing and boosting productivity. It takes the form of activities that help employees prepare for more complex or demanding tasks. Training is vital for developing human capital as it equips employees with the skills, abilities, and information they need to carry out their responsibilities (Tzafirir, 2005). The training goal is to notice a change in the behaviour of those who have gone through it. This means that trainees will learn new artistic skills, technical knowledge, and talents on the job in the most efficient way possible to assist the organization in meeting its goals (Tesfu, 2019).

2.5 Employee Performance

Companies go to great lengths to please their customers, but employee satisfaction is frequently overlooked. On the other hand, customers will not be satisfied unless employees are happy because happy employees will do more work, which will please customers (Ahmad, 2012). Employee motivation affects performance because motivated employees work harder, resulting in better results (Azar and Shafiqhi, 2013; Azar and Shafiqhi, 2013; Dahkoul (2018) Al Mehrzi and Singh (2016) define performance as an individual's outcome or success in carrying out duties over time compared to other possibilities such as work standards, targets, or specified criteria. When it comes to doing projects on time, job discipline is crucial. On the other hand, companies must consider motivating factors, as motivation is a tool for encouraging employees to complete tasks assigned to them (Halbesleben and Wheeler, 2008) (Hermina and Yosepha, April 2019).

2.6 Theories Related to Employee Performance

2.6.1 The Expectancy Theory of Victor Vroom

The expectancy theory by Victor Vroom is among the most well-known incentive theories. The approach is built on three assumptions: effort leads to performance, substantial performance leads to organizational incentives (bonus, salary, and promotion), and the reward

will be customized to the individual's objectives (Robbins and Judge, 2013). As a result, the theory focuses on the three connections (expectancy, instrumentality, and valence) (Tesfu, Effects of working environment on employee performance, June, 2019). The degree to which a person believes that achieving a given level of performance will result in the intended outcome. Unless there is a clear link between favourable performance reports and rewards, little effort will be put into earning those high assessment marks (Tesfu, June 2019).

2.6.2 Adam's Equity (Fairness) Theory

Equity theory, a topic in industrial psychology, concerns people's perceptions of how equally they are treated at work. The notion is based on a person's subjective appraisal of the fairness of the reward they received in comparison to the inputs (which can include several characteristics such as effort, experience, education, and so on) and rewards they received from others (Tesfu, June 2019).

2.6.3 Herzberg's Two Factor Theory

Frederick Herzberg first proposed the Two-Factor Theory in 1959. This study is based on a theory that several researchers have investigated to understand better the relationship between the working environment and a worker's performance. Herzberg identified two attributes that impact employees' work attitudes and levels of performance: motivation and hygiene variables. Herzberg identified two features that affect employees' work attitudes and levels of performance: motivation and hygiene variables. The year 2007 is one of the most significant in the history of the United States of America (Robbins and Judge). The basis of the concept has received much praise for motivating people to give it their utmost at work. More research has revealed that intrinsic variables, such as Herzberg's motivational needs, inspire employees more than any other factor (Tesfu, 2019).

2.7 Conceptual framework

Source: adapted from (Ameen and Baharom, March, 2019).

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Population

The study's target demographic is employees and middle-level managers from two manufacturing companies, AFI and JEMA, out of the ten currently operating manufacturing enterprises in Mogadishu. Employees and middle-level managers from a few selected enterprises in Mogadishu, Somalia, were the survey's respondents. The researcher chose the two because of their extensive experience in the industry.

3.2 Sample Size

The target demographic for this study was 300 employees from various industrial enterprises in Mogadishu. According to (Nduku, Mwenda, & Wachira, 2015), the researcher adopted a sample size from the literature. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings, the sample size for this study was 172 respondents, including management and staff. The researcher computed the sample size using Solvent's approach to generate a researchable sample size, with a maximum permitted error of 5%.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Na^2}$$

N stands for the population

n. stands the sample

a. stands acceptable error

$$n = \frac{300}{1 + 300(0.05)^2}$$

$$=172$$

Purposive sampling is a type in which the researcher chooses study participants based on their ability to provide accurate data or information.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDING

4.1 Demographic Data

Table 4.1: Demographics Profile of the Respondents

Age	frequency	percent	valid percent
18-24	34	19.8	19.8
25-36	93	54.1	54.1
37-43	38	22.1	22.1
44 and above	7	4.1	4.1
Total	172	100	100
Gender			
Male	131	76.2	76.2
Female	41	23.8	23.8
Total	172	100	100
Marital status			

Single	84	48.8	48.8
Married	88	51.2	51.2
Total	172	100	100
Educational level			
Master degree	39	22.7	22.7
Bachelor	112	65.1	65.1
Diploma	21	12.2	12.2
Total	172	100	100
Work Experience			
Less than one year	30	17.4	17.4
1-5 years	98	57.0	57.0
5-10 years	37	21.5	21.5
More than ten years	7	4.1	4.1
Total	172	100	100
Position			
Administrative	60	34.9	34.9
None administrative	112	65.1	65.1
Total	172	100	100
Ownership			
Owner	30	17.4	17.4
Employee	142	82.6	82.6
Total	172	100	100
Size of Company			
Small (10-49 employees)	94	54.7	54.7
Medium (50-249 employees)	78	45.3	45.3
Total	172	100	100

Source: Primary Data (2022)

The age of respondents (19.8%) was between 18_24 while (44.1%) of the respondents were between 25_36, (22.1%) of the respondents were between 37-43 and (4.1%) of the respondents were between 44 and above. On the other hand, the gender of the respondents was male and female. As a result, the researcher discovered that most respondents (76.2%) were male, while the remaining (23.8%) were female; most of the covers were male. The researcher asked the respondents their marital status; however, most respondents were married (51.2%) while the single respondents were (48.8%). On the other side, the respondent was asked about their education level in the involvement of educational background. Therefore 22.7% of the respondents had master's degrees, 65.1% had bachelor's degrees, and the remaining 12.2% were diplomas. Also, the respondent was asked about their experience in the involvement of work by The researcher. However, (17.4%) of respondents were less than one year, while (57.0%) of respondents were 1 to 5 years, (21.5.2%) of respondents were 5 to 10 years, and (4.1%) were ten and above years. Therefore, the researcher indicates that most respondents 'experience was 1 to 5 years. The position titles of the respondents were administrative and non-administrative. Therefore, the researcher found that (34.9%) of the respondents were administrative, while the remaining (65.1%) were non-administrative, and the majority of the cover were non-administrative; on the other hand, the respondents were asked if they were owners or not, but

the researcher was found that 17.4% were owner while 82.6 were employees. The final demographic information that was invited to the respondents by the researcher was the size of their company, and the result found that the majority of the respondents (54.7%) said their size of the company was medium, while (45.3 %) said their size of the company is small.

4.2 The effect of working hours on employee performance

Table 4.2: feel that long hours worked opportunities encourage me to work better

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	64	37.2	37.2	37.2
Disagree	38	22.1	22.1	59.3
Neutral	17	9.9	9.9	69.2
Agree	46	26.7	26.7	95.9
Strongly agree	7	4.1	4.1	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2022

Table 4.4.1 and Figure: 4.1 showed that the majority of respondents, 64(37.2%), firmly disagreed that the employee feels that long hours worked opportunities encourage to work better, 38(22.1%) disagreed with it, 17(9.9%) were Neutral, 4(4.1%) were agreed on it, and while 46(26.7) were strongly agreed.

Table 4.3: I have unachievable deadlines at work

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	42	24.4	24.4	24.4
Disagree	55	32.0	32.0	56.4
Neutral	22	12.8	12.8	69.2
Agree	44	25.6	25.6	94.8
Strongly agree	9	5.2	5.2	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

Source: primary data, 2022

Table 4.4.2 and figure 4.2 indicated that the majority of respondents, 55(32.0%), disagreed that I have unachievable deadlines at work, 42 (24.4%) were strongly opposed, 22 (12.8%) were neutral, 44 (25.6%) agreed and while only 9 (5.2%) were strongly agreed on it.

4.3 The effect of workload on employee performance

Table 4.4: Duties delegated to me are occasionally outside my scope of practice, which makes me feel inept and frustrated.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	21	12.2	12.2	12.2
	Disagree	14	8.1	8.1	20.3
	Neutral	13	7.6	7.6	27.9
	Agree	101	58.7	58.7	86.6
	Strongly agree	23	13.4	13.4	100.0
	Total	172	100.0	100.0	

Source: primary data, 2022

According to table 4.4.6 and figure 4.6, the majority of respondents, 101 (58.7 %), agreed that my delegated duties sometimes fall outside my scope of practice, making me feel inadequate and frustrated. Only 13 (7.6%) were neutral, 21 (12.2%) strongly disagreed, 14 (8.1%) disagreed, and only 23 (13.4%) strongly agreed. According to the researcher, most respondents disagree that working hours can be flexible, implying that employee performance will suffer if they are.

4.5 The effect of training on employee performance

Table 4.6: Initial training received when hired me

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	19	11.0	11.0	11.0
	Disagree	7	4.1	4.1	15.1
	Neutral	17	9.9	9.9	25.0
	Agree	87	50.6	50.6	75.6
	Strongly agree	42	24.4	24.4	100.0
	Total	172	100.0	100.0	

Source: primary data, 2022

Based on the findings, 87 respondents agreed that there is Initial training at the company when hiring employees with a percentage of 50.6%, while 42 strongly agreed with a percentage of 24.4%. Nineteen of the population strongly disagreed with the percentage of 11.0% that Initial training received when hired in the company, and 7 of the respondents disagreed with 41%. 17 of the respondents were neutral, with a percentage of 9.9%. This implies that 50.6% of the respondents, to a greater extent, strongly agreed that initial training is received by employees when hired in the company.

5.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

According to the descriptive statistics of the variables, most employees strongly disagree that long hours of working opportunities assist them in working better. 38. (22.1 %). In the second question of the first goal, "working hours," most employees objected that employees have unattainable targets at work, 42 (24.4 %) strongly disagreed, 22 (12.8 %) were neutral, 44 (25.6 %) agreed, and while just 9 (5.2 %) highly agreed. The third question, "working hours," elicited the following responses: 66 (38.4%) disputed that employees face unrealistic time demands at work, 21 (12.2%) strongly disagreed, 16 (9.3%) were indifferent, 43 (25.0%) agreed, and only 26 (15.1%) highly agreed. In the last two questions, 59 (34.3 %) of employees disagreed that working time can be flexible, 20 (11.6 %) were neutral, 22 (12.8 %) strongly disagreed, and 35 (20.3 %) agreed. Only 36 (20.9 %) strongly disagreed, and in question five, 56 (32.6 %) disagreed that employees cannot take enough breaks at work. There were 21 (12.2%) who were neutral, 18 (10.5%) who strongly disagreed, 37 (21.5%) who agreed, and just 40 (23.3%) who highly agreed. According to the findings, most respondents disputed that employees were given enough breaks, implying that their performance would suffer if they were not given enough breaks.

This study aimed to examine how working conditions affected employee performance at a few selected industrial firms in Mogadishu, Somalia. Additionally, the study looked into the effects of working hours, workload, and training on employee performance. To achieve these goals, respondents were asked to respond to a series of things by selecting one based on their impressions. Data on these objectives was examined using the SPSS descriptive statistics tool, which produced the following frequency table: questionnaire from manufacturing company employees. Furthermore, most of the reviewed data suggested that employee productivity is influenced by working hours, workload, and training.

The study's findings have successfully confirmed that the study's key objectives were met. Furthermore, at manufacturing enterprises in Mogadishu, Somalia, the three determinants of working conditions have a beneficial effect on employee productivity. Again, the comprehensive study reveals that all indications of job working conditions, such as working hours, workload, and training, have a 65 percent impact on all measures of employee productivity. After reviewing all the findings, it is evident that working conditions directly impact employee productivity. These three variables positively impact working hours while harming workload, implying that effective working hours will boost productivity. Employees today require good working conditions to increase their productivity while maintaining reasonable working hours and burden and training and development in their workplace.

In this study, working conditions impact employee productivity in the case of manufacturing enterprises; in general, the researchers conclude that operating conditions affect employee performance. To connect the preceding studies, Thramma Bhaga (2003) investigated working conditions and employee productivity in South Africa and discovered that working conditions positively and negatively affect productivity (Ali, Ali and Adan, October 2013).

According to Bornstein (2007), productivity and service delivery suffer when employees are subjected to stressful working conditions. On the other hand, better working conditions increase productivity and positively impact the provision of services. (Ali, 2013).

6.0 REFERENCES

- Alfiyah¹, N., & Riyanto, S. (2019). The Effect of Compensation, Work Environment and Training on Employees' Performance of Politeknik LP3I Jakarta. *Work*, 2, 49.
- Ali, A. Y. S., Ali, A. A., & Adan, A. A. (2013). Working conditions and employees' productivity in manufacturing companies in sub-Saharan African context: Case of Somalia. *Educational Research International*, 2(2), 67-78.
- Ameen, A., & Baharom, M. N. ASSESSING THE EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN AN ORGANISATION: A THEORETICAL DISCUSSION
- Ali, A. Y. S., Ali, A. A., & Adan, A. A. (2013). Working conditions and employees' productivity in manufacturing companies in sub-Saharan African context: Case of Somalia. *Educational research international*, 2(2), 67-78.
- ALEMNEW, G. (2020). THE EFFECT OF LABOR UNION ACTIVITIES ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN ETHIO TELECOM (THE CASE STUDY OF ETHIO TELECOM, NORTH WEST REGION) (Doctoral dissertation).
- Bashir, A., Amir, A., Jawaad, M., & Hasan, T. (2020). Work conditions and job performance: An indirect Conditional effect of motivation. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1), 1801961.
- Bushiri, C. P. (2014). The impact of working environment on employees' performance, the case of Institute of Finance Management in Dar es Salaam (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania).
- Bonsu, C. A., & Kusi, A. (2014). Effects of motivation on job performance of local government workers in Ghana: A case study of Atwima Nwabiagya District Assembly in the Ashanti Region. *International Journal of Management Sciences*, 2(8), 337-350.
- Chaudhry, N. I., Jariko, M. A., Mushtaque, T., Mahesar, H. A., & Ghani, Z. (2017). Impact of working environment and training & development on organization performance through mediating role of employee engagement and job satisfaction. *European Journal of Training and Development Studies*, 4(2), 33-48.
- Chaudhry, N. I., Jariko, M. A., Mushtaque, T., Mahesar, H. A., & Ghani, Z. (2017). Impact of working environment and training & development on organization performance through mediating role of employee engagement and job satisfaction. *European Journal of Training and Development Studies*, 4(2), 33-48.
- DAKHOUL, Z. M. (2018). The determinants of employee performance in Jordanian organizations. *Journal of Economics Finance and Accounting*, 5(1), 137-143.
- Eluka, J. C., Agu, O. A., & Nwonu, C. O. (2015). Improving and promoting ethical behavior in business relations: Evidence from Nigeria. In *Information and Knowledge Management* (Vol. 5, No. 5, pp. 80-88).
- Ipole, P. A., & Okpa, J. T. (2019). Working conditions and employees' productivity in Cross river State civil service, Nigeria.
- Khan, S. H., Azhar, Z., Parveen, S., Naeem, F., & Sohail, M. M. (2012). Exploring the Impact of Infrastructure, Pay Incentives and Workplace Environment on Employees' Performance (A Case Study of Sargodha University). *Asian Journal of Empirical Research*, 2(4), 118-140.
- han, S. H., Azhar, Z., Parveen, S., Naeem, F., & Sohail, M. M. (2012). Exploring the Impact of Infrastructure, Pay Incentives and Workplace Environment on Employees' Performance (A Case Study of Sargodha University). *Asian Journal of Empirical Research*, 2(4), 118-140.

- Malik, M. I., Ahmad, A., Gomez, S. F., & Ali, M. (2011). A study of work environment and employees performance in Pakistan. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(34), 13227-13232.
- Malik, M. I., Ahmad, A., Gomez, S. F., & Ali, M. (2011). A study of work environment and employees performance in Pakistan. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(34), 13227-13232.
- Mamun, M. Z. A., & Khan, M. Y. H. (2020). A Theoretical Study On Factors Influencing Employees Performance, Rewards and Motivation within Organization
- Manu, C. A. (2016). The effects of work environment on employees productivity in government organizations. A case study of Obuasi Municipal Assembly (Doctoral dissertation).
- Manu, C. A. (2016). The effects of work environment on employees productivity in government organizations. A case study of Obuasi Municipal Assembly (Doctoral dissertation).
- Massoudi, A. H., & Hamdi, S. S. A. (2017). The Consequence of work environment on Employees Productivity. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 19(01), 35-42.
- Mokaya, S. O., Musau, J. L., Wagoki, J., & Karanja, K. (2013). Effects of organizational work conditions on employee job satisfaction in the hotel industry in Kenya. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, 2(2), 79-90.
- Rizwan, M., & Mukhtar, A. (2014). Preceding to employee satisfaction and turnover intention. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(3), 87.
- Riyanto, S., Sutrisno, A., & Ali, H. (2017). The impact of working motivation and working environment on employees' performance in Indonesia stock exchange. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 7(3), 342-348
- TESHOME, B. (2021). THE EFFECT OF WORKING CONDITION ON EMPLOYEE'S PERFORMANCE: IN CASE OF DASHEN BREWERY SHARE COMPANY, GONDAR ETHIOPIA (Doctoral dissertation, uog).
- Utin, N. H., & Yosepha, S. Y. (2019). The Model of Employee Performance. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 9(3), 69.
- Westerman, J. W., & Simmons, B. L. (2007). The effects of work environment on the Personality-performance relationship: An exploratory study. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 288-305.